

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

BINAR CLASSIFICATION OF STUDENTS' PSYCHOLOGICAL CONDITION USING XGBOOST

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Abstract

Nowadays, machine learning algorithms are used to solve issues in each sphere, including the field of education. In this article, we will consider a classification model based on the XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) machine learning algorithm to classify the psychological condition of schoolchildren into "stressed" and "non-stressed" classes. Currently, there is an increase in the number of factors that negatively affect the psychological condition of students, so this issue is important. Because excessive stress prevents students from receiving effective education. A dataset was created based on the psychological characteristics of schoolchildren for binary classification. A web application was created for the issue considered in the article. The XGBoost regularization of the binary classification in the article effectively solved the issue of overfitting due to the optimization of gradients and parallel computing capabilities. 326 students at school took psychological test via the web application. We will discuss the results in the paper.

Keywords: XGBoost, Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, student, psychological condition.

Introduction.

It is known that school education is the main educational stage in every person's life. Getting a quality education at this stage is important for every person's future. By identifying and eliminating factors that negatively affect the psychological condition of schoolchildren, it is possible to ensure that students get quality education. In the modern education system, it is important to analyze the mental and psychological condition of students. If the stress state is detected early, students will be able to receive timely help. Studies conducted on determining the stress level of school students show that various factors, including sleep quality, family environment, academic load, and level of communication with friends, play an important role in the occurrence of stress. Therefore, monitoring the psychological condition of students and dividing them into "stressed" and "non-stressed" classes based on various data is important for effective education [1]. This article considers the issue of assessing the psychological condition of school students using the XGBoost algorithm and dividing them into two classes, namely "stressed" and "non-stressed". The article also presents a mathematical model of the problem. In modern educational institutions, maintaining the mental health of students and early detection of stress levels are becoming one of the most important tasks. Stress among students can negatively affect their academic performance, social life, and health. In particular, increased mental pressure leads to mental fatigue, decreased motivation, and depression-like states in students. The use of machine learning algorithms is of great importance in solving these problems. In this process, it is necessary to recognize that machine learning algorithms, especially the XGBoost algorithm, are one of the effective algorithms [2]. The XGBoost algorithm is a powerful machine learning method based on gradient boosting. The model differs from other algorithms in its high accuracy and

fast performance characteristics. This algorithm is adapted to work with large volumes of complex data and is successfully used in classification problems. In our study, a mathematical model and an application corresponding to the model were developed to assess the stress level of school students based on various data collected from them using the XGBoost algorithm. The aim of this study is to use the XGBoost algorithm to classify the psychological condition of schoolchildren into "stressed" and "non-stressed" classes. It also aims to test the effectiveness of the algorithm on practical data. Diagnostic tools for stress assessment are usually time-consuming and may be subject to subjective factors. The application of machine learning algorithms to this process increases accuracy and speeds up the diagnostic process [3]. Thus, school psychologists and teachers will be able to take the necessary measures in a timely manner. Previous studies on stress prediction have used logistic regression, neural networks, and decision tree algorithms. Compared with the other algorithms listed above, XGBoost offers a more efficient and flexible solution based on gradient boosting. XGBoost is an optimized version of the gradient boosting algorithm. It stands out from other machine learning algorithms with its high accuracy, fast performance, and efficiency. The XGBoost algorithm is based on Classification and Regression Trees decision trees. The XGBoost algorithm uses multi-core processing to increase the speed of solving the problem. The algorithm also has special regularization methods to reduce the risk of overfitting, and the algorithm can be applied to solve regression and classification problems [4].

We overview several articles on the topic of the article. [5] balanced test set was created using Knowledge-Based Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique. The XGBoost model assessed students' mental health based on Symptom Checklist-90 scores. With parameter optimization, the model solved the

problem with 92% accuracy. The anxiety level of Chinese undergraduate students during online learning during the COVID-19 period was analyzed using the XGBoost model [6]. The model demonstrated high prediction accuracy with Area Under the (Receiver Operating Characteristic) Curve equals to 0.89. In addition, the model allowed educators to be aware of students' anxiety levels early. Based on health survey data from a Japanese national university, the XGBoost model predicted students' mental health problems in 2020 and 2021. The one-year transfer function increased the stability of the models [7]. A model for predicting mental health risks in young people with mental health disorders was developed using XGBoost. The model results were validated with a 100×5 -fold k-fold test statistic with an accuracy of Area Under the (Receiver Operating Characteristic) Curve equals to 0.88 [8]. Data collected from 52,054 students aged 10–17 in the United States were analyzed based on demographic, clinical, and social factors, and models for detecting depression and anxiety in students were created using XGBoost. SHapley Additive exPlanations analysis identifies key predictors and paves the way for early intervention. The model was able to predict depression and anxiety in students with high accuracy [9]. In order to assess the risk of mental health among adolescents in 2024, XGBoost and Random Forest models were used based on real-world data. The 10 predictors that most affect the mental state of adolescents were identified. The model is tested based on Area Under the (Receiver Operating Characteristic) Curve. The results were used to develop early prevention strategies among adolescents. The XGBoost- Hippopotamus Optimization Algorithm module was tested to classify depression and anxiety into four classes based on data from 5019 adolescents during the COVID-19 period. The model demonstrated high accuracy and factor analysis with SHapley Additive exPlanations and improved psychological condition prediction. A study comparing the results of XGBoost and Light Gradient Boosting Machine algorithms in identifying mental health problems in adolescents was published in the journal *Procedia Computer Science*. The optimization of model parameters, reduction of uncertainty, and generation efficiency are analyzed. XGBoost gave stable results [10]. Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine, K-Nearest Neighbors, logistic logic, decision tree, Random Forest, XGBoost, and Natural Gradient Boosting models were tested to assess mental illness among Asian students. XGBoost showed the highest results in identifying factors of social support and childhood conditions [11]. This study uses a real training dataset that includes various characteristics of students. The XGBoost model has several advantages over other machine learning algorithms.

XGBoost is an optimized, fast, and scalable version of gradient boosting algorithms. It has high accuracy and fast training capabilities for classification problems. The main goal of the study is to create a model for predicting the stress state of school students and classifying them into classes using the XGBoost algorithm, based on various factors. The characteristics include: age, gender, sleep duration, academic perfor-

mance, sports participation, family environment, communication with friends, and psychological test results. Based on these characteristics, the XGBoost algorithm processes the data and determines the probability of stress for each student. In 2025, 326 students at a school took psychological test through platform created based on the XGBoost. At the same time, the test results are also discussed in the article.

Methodology.

For binary classification of psychological condition of students, i.e., for dividing the psychological condition of school students into “stressed” or “unstressed” classes, student characteristics (for example, sleep duration, academic performance, family environment, psychological test results, etc.) are used. To solve this problem, a machine learning algorithm is used, since traditional psychological assessment methods are time-consuming and in many cases subjective. During the creation of the model, its mathematical model is also considered. For the issue under consideration in the article, a data set about school students is used to create and test the model. This data includes the following characteristics:

This training dataset was created based on international studies Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development and Programme for International Student Assessment. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development and Program for International Student Assessment datasets were created taking into account the main characteristics of the psychological condition of school students. This data underwent preliminary cleaning and normalization stages. The dataset was split into 70% training data and 30% test data. The synthetic training dataset created consists of 10,000 sample data.

When creating the training dataset, we took the main factors that affect the psychological condition of students.

Training dataset properties:

Age (integer) - Student's age (range 10–18);

Gender (nominal) - two values, i.e. male or female;

Sleep duration (integer) - Daily sleep duration in hours (4–12 hours);

Academic performance (real number) - Student's academic score (range 0–100);

Sports participation (categorical) - Regular sports participation (binary, i.e. yes/no);

Family environment (integer) - Level of communication with parents, assessed on a 1–10-point scale;

Psychological test results (real number) - Student test scores (0–100) to measure psychological stability;

After creating training dataset for the model, we will create mathematical model for the binar classification.

So, if we start by constructing a mathematical model of the problem under consideration, the problem is a classification problem i.e., $y \in \{0,1\}$

$y = 0$ – the student is not in the condition of stress,

$y = 1$ – the student is under stress.

The input to the model is a vector of student-specific features $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$, where each x_i represents individual student factors (e.g., sleep duration, academic performance, social activity level, etc.). The task of the model is to accurately predict the output (stress or not) based on the input features [9].

Formula (1) represents the mathematical model of the XGBoost algorithm.

If $D = \{(x_i, y_i)\}$ is the training data set, where x_i is the input vector, y_i is the actual output, then the objective function is defined as in Formula 1:

$$L(\phi) = \sum_{i=1}^n l(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + \sum_{k=1}^K \Omega(f_k). \quad (1)$$

Where:

l – is the loss function (for log loss classification),

$\Omega(f_k)$ – is the function that regulates the complexity of the model.

The XGBoost algorithm builds a new tree that minimizes the objective function at each iteration Formula (2).

$$\hat{y}_i' = \hat{y}_i^{t-1} + f_t(x_i). \quad (2)$$

This process focuses on reducing model errors [10] using subsequent trees.

The log loss function is used for classification Formula (3).

$$l(y, \hat{y}) = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)). \quad (3)$$

Where

y_i – actual value (0 or 1),

\hat{y}_i – predicted value,

n – number of samples.

The loss function helps minimize the difference between predicted values and actual values.

Above we created a training dataset and a mathematical model. Now we will create the algorithm in order to classify students' psychological condition into two classes using XGBoost.

The algorithm created based on the model is as follows:

- Data preparation
- Data cleaning and preprocessing
- Data division into training and testing datasets
- Creating an XGBoost model
- Model training
- Model evaluation
- Using the model, that is, when a new student's data is entered, this model is used to determine his psychological condition (stress or not)

The web application was created based on the algorithm. Students took psychological test via the web-application. We will review the test results in the next chapter.

Main part.

In this research, a model for predicting the stress state of school students using the XGBoost machine

learning algorithm was developed. 326 school students took a psychological test on the platform created based on the model. Table 1 represents the confusion matrix of the XGBoost model, which consists of the results of the students' psychological tests.

Table 1.

Confusion matrix of XGBoost.	
Stressed	Non Stressed
309	7
5	3

The model's Accuracy in classifying the issue was 96.30%, Precision = 97.78%, Recall = 98.41%, F1-Score = 97.94%, Specificity = 30.00% and False Positive Rate = 70.00%. The value of each metric showed high indicators and The XGBoost model effectively performed the binary classification issue. The value of each metric is discussed in the following chapter. The results show that the XGBoost algorithm showed high accuracy in detecting stress among students. This is due to the algorithm's ability to effectively identify relationships between complex features [11].

Findings.

The model achieved very high Recall = 98.41% and Precision = 97.78% in detecting positive cases. This means that almost all true positive examples were correctly identified. At the same time, the results showed a balance between F1-Score = 97.94%, precision and recall [12]. These results increase the applicability of the model, especially in areas where the detection of positive cases is important. However, it is worth paying serious attention to the low results of the model in the negative classes (Specificity = 30.00%). This low specificity means that the model incorrectly identifies many true negative examples as positive (FP Rate = 70.00%). Therefore, the model also needs to be further improved in the negative class. Overall, the model performed excellently in detecting the positive class. However, additional measures should be taken to increase the sensitivity in the negative classes. In the future, improving the information balance, adjusting class weights, and testing threshold optimization methods will significantly improve the overall performance of the model [13]. In this study, a model was developed to predict and classify the psychological condition of school students using the XGBoost machine learning algorithm. The model classifies students' stress levels into "stressed" or "unstressed" classes based on factors such as age, gender, sleep duration, academic performance, sports participation, family environment, and psychological test results [14]. Overall, this study demonstrated that using machine learning algorithms to identify students' psychological condition is an effective method. By further improving the model, the possibilities of identifying and helping students who are prone to stress can be expanded. Early identification of stress states among students has a positive impact on their academic success and psychological well-being. However, accurate identification of stress is a complex process. This situation is associated with various internal and external factors. Traditional assessment methods (e.g., questionnaires or psychological tests) are of-

ten subjective and time-consuming. Therefore, machine learning algorithms, particularly XGBoost, are highly effective at identifying complex relationships and evaluating different factors together. In addition, the model is unexpensive. Therefore, the model can also be applied in the education systems of poor countries. The model is also convenient to use in various situations, for example, in quarantine situations and in cases of natural disasters.

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